

1 **Towards understanding the behavior of polyelectrolyte –**
2 **surfactant mixtures at the water / vapor interface closer to**
3 **technologically-relevant conditions**

4 Sara Llamas,¹ Laura Fernández-Peña,¹ Andrew Akanno,^{1,2} Eduardo Guzmán,^{1,2,*}
5 Víctor Ortega,² Francisco Ortega,^{1,2} Aurelio G. Csaky,² Richard A. Campbell,⁴ and
6 Ramón G. Rubio^{1,2,*}

7 ¹Departamento de Química Física I-Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Ciudad
8 Universitaria s/n, 28040 Madrid, Spain

9 ²Instituto Pluridisciplinar-Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Avda. Juan XXIII, 1, 28040
10 Madrid, Spain

11 ³Institut Laue-Langevin, 71 avenue des Martyrs, CS 20156, 38042 Grenoble, Cedex 9,
12 France

13 **Published in Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics 20 (2018) 1395-1407**

14 <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7CP05528E>

15
16
17
18 *To whom correspondence should be sent: eduardogs@quim.ucm.es and
19 rgrubio@quim.ucm.es

1 Abstract

2 Polyelectrolyte – surfactant mixtures and their interactions with fluid interfaces are an
3 important research field due to their use in technological applications. Most of the existing
4 knowledge on these systems is based on models in which the polyelectrolyte concentration is
5 around 50 times lower than that used in commercial formulations. The present works marks a
6 step to close the gap on the understanding of their behavior under more practically-relevant
7 conditions. The adsorption of concentrated mixtures of poly(diallyldimethyl)ammonium
8 chloride and sodium N-lauroyl-N-methyltaurate at the water / vapor interface with a crude
9 mixing protocol has been studied by different surface tension techniques, Brewster angle
10 microscopy, neutron reflectometry, and various bulk characterization techniques. Kinetically-
11 trapped aggregates formed during mixing influence the interfacial morphology of mixtures
12 produced in an equilibrium one-phase region, yet fluctuations in the surface tension isotherm
13 result depending on the tensiometric technique applied. At low bulk surfactant
14 concentrations, the free surfactant concentration is very low, and the interfacial composition
15 matches the trend of the bulk complexes, which is a behavior that has not been observed in
16 studies on more dilute mixtures. Nevertheless, a transition to synergistic co-adsorption of
17 complexes and free surfactant is observed at the higher bulk surfactant concentrations
18 studied. This transition appears to be a special feature of these more concentrated mixtures,
19 which deserves attention in future studies of systems with additional components.

20

1 **1. Introduction**

2 The physico-chemical behavior of polymer – surfactant mixtures in the bulk solution and
3 upon adsorption at interfaces, both fluid and solid, has attracted considerable interest in
4 recent years due to their importance in many technological and industrial applications,
5 ranging from drug delivery systems to mineral processing, and from tertiary oil recovery to
6 the development of cosmetic formulations for hair care.¹⁻⁶ Among these applications, the
7 mixtures involving polyelectrolytes and surfactants bearing opposite charges are generally
8 accounted for as the most important.^{2, 6} In this case, the applications take advantage of the
9 chemical nature of the components, structural features of the formed complexes in solution
10 and the rich phase diagram resulting from the formation of macroscopic aggregates.^{1, 3}
11 Despite the extensive research on these systems, many aspects remain not fully understood,
12 especially those in which the interaction of the mixtures with fluid interfaces is considered.
13 This is in part due to the complex interplay of interactions, both electrostatic and
14 hydrophobic, existing in this type of systems, which leads to the appearance of complex
15 phase diagrams and makes their adsorption at fluid interfaces difficult to understand.^{4, 7-15}
16 Historically these systems were studied extensively using surface tension measurements by
17 the groups of Goddard¹⁶⁻¹⁷ and Langevin.¹⁸⁻²⁰ However, the seminal works on the
18 compositional characterization of oppositely charged polyelectrolyte – surfactant layers at the
19 water / vapor interface were performed by Thomas and Penfold who also exploited neutron
20 reflectometry.²¹⁻²³ These works represented an important step forward in the understanding of
21 the role of different parameters on the interfacial behavior of polyelectrolyte – surfactant
22 mixtures at chemical equilibrium. More recently, much attention has been paid by Campbell
23 and Varga to linking the interfacial properties of these systems to the bulk phase behavior
24 including non-equilibrium effects both in the bulk and at the water / vapor interface.²⁴⁻²⁸ They

PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 used the same two techniques in addition to other complementary tools such as ellipsometry
2 and Brewster angle microscopy as well as a range of bulk characterization techniques.

3 As hinted above, a key characteristic of these systems is their interesting bulk phase
4 behavior.²⁹⁻³⁰ At bulk compositions where the formed complexes have a low charge, they
5 spontaneously aggregate over time, and eventually precipitate separates from a depleted
6 supernatant that contains small ions by sinking to the bottom or floating to the top of the
7 samples – these compositions mark the equilibrium two-phase region.³¹⁻³² With a greater
8 amount of either component, the formed complexes have sufficient colloidal stability that
9 they do not spontaneously aggregate, and these compositions mark the equilibrium one-phase
10 regions. An important complication is related to concentration gradients present when the
11 components are mixed, because if complexes formed locally in the sample experience a lack
12 of colloidal stability, aggregates can form on a sub-second time scale that may be insoluble
13 once mixing is complete a few second later.³³ As a consequence, the properties of the
14 mixtures depend critically on the protocol used for mixing the components,³⁴⁻³⁵ and this has
15 evidently led to contradictory results in experiments published over the years that introduce
16 further difficulties into predicting their behavior. Moreover, the mixing protocol can be
17 different for different industrial applications, which is an issue that is taken into account in
18 the present work. It has been shown systematically over the last few years that the kinetically-
19 trapped aggregates can affect or even dominate the measured interfacial properties.²⁵⁻²⁷

20 Seemingly in contrast to these experimental studies, however, most of the theoretical studies
21 published so far are based on a thermodynamic framework at chemical equilibrium such as
22 mean field approaches,³⁶ which do not take into account effects of kinetically-trapped
23 aggregates that can dominate the actual measured steady state properties.³⁴⁻³⁵

24 Surface tension is probably the most common property used for the study of the adsorption of
25 these mixtures at the water / vapor interface. In most cases polyelectrolytes are not surface
PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 active except at high concentrations. However, two key non-equilibrium characteristics of
2 these systems have been systematically described:²⁴ the slow approach to equilibrium limited
3 by the time scale of precipitation (i.e. aggregate growth and settling), and a perturbation from
4 equilibrium as a result of the sample handling when formed precipitate encounters the water /
5 vapor interface (i.e. when material is spread to form a kinetically-trapped film). In these
6 cases, steady state properties can be measured that are far from equilibrium. Nevertheless,
7 even though the surface tension is formally an equilibrium property, for the sense of
8 simplicity hereinafter we will refer to the steady state property measured in the present work
9 as surface tension.

10 Mixtures formed by a polycation, poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride) (PDADMAC)
11 and the anionic surfactant sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) at the water / vapor interface are one
12 of the most studied in recent years. This system shows a non-monotonic dependence of the
13 surface tension on the bulk surfactant concentration (at fixed bulk polyelectrolyte
14 concentration), exhibiting a surface tension peak in its isotherm.¹⁴ The maximum of this peak
15 has been shown to be positioned on the phase boundary (i.e. the edge of the equilibrium two-
16 phase region that has the lowest bulk surfactant concentration).²⁵ The peak cannot be
17 described in terms of simple adsorption models such as Langmuir or Frumkin, which are
18 based on all the components of the system being in the same phase.³⁷

19 PDADMAC has also been chosen as the polycation in this work because it is used as a
20 conditioning agent in hair cosmetic products, flocculant agent for water treatment, retention
21 agent in paper fabrication, and the fabrication of polyelectrolyte multilayers.³⁸⁻⁴¹ For the
22 anionic surfactant, we have chosen sodium N-lauroyl-N-methyltaurate (SLMT), as it is less
23 susceptible to the degradation into highly surface-active impurities than SDS.⁴² In a previous
24 work we have studied the adsorption of this mixture at water / solid interface for the
25 evaluation of its potential applicability as hair conditioning system because it is less irritant
PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 than the sodium lauryl sulfonate that is present in most of the current commercial shampoo
2 formulations.^{39, 43} The present study extends the scope of the previous one to understanding
3 the behavior of such mixtures at water / vapor interface. The surface tension isotherm has
4 been measured using five different types of tensiometer in order to identify then appropriately
5 categorize any experimental artifacts that could affect the measured values.⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶ In addition to
6 the study of the surface tension, neutron reflectometry experiments have been carried out to
7 obtain independently a quantification of the interfacial composition of the mixtures, and
8 Brewster angle microscopy has been used to image the presence of kinetically-trapped
9 aggregates at the interface. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first one in which a
10 combination of different tensiometric techniques, neutron reflectometry and Brewster angle
11 microscopy experiments are used for the study of the interfacial properties of a
12 polyelectrolyte – surfactant system.

13 Most of the papers published so far have focused on mixtures with polyelectrolyte
14 concentrations well below the overlapping concentration, c^* , i.e. the concentration above
15 which the physico-chemical properties of polyelectrolytes lose their dependence on the
16 molecular weight,⁴⁷⁻⁴⁸ which is far from the situation found in most technological
17 applications. For example, it is estimated that when a shampoo is applied to the wet hair, the
18 polyelectrolyte concentration is about 5 – 10 times c^* for PDADMAC, which is around 0.08
19 wt%.^{39, 49-51} As a step towards more industrially-relevant formulations, the bulk
20 polyelectrolyte concentration used in the present work is 0.5 wt%, which is at least an order
21 of magnitude greater than the concentrations used in fundamental studies in the literature.^{21, 25}
22 In addition, the samples are all pH-adjusted and a high ionic strength of added inert
23 electrolyte is used. The equilibrium two-phase region would be expected to be at greater bulk
24 surfactant concentrations than those measured, and this is an assumption that is objectively
25 tested. Nevertheless, it is understood that effects from kinetically-trapped aggregates formed
PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 during mixing can affect interfacial properties in the equilibrium one-phase regions,²⁶⁻²⁷ so
2 this possibility is also examined. The critical mixing of the components is carried out by
3 diluting concentrated samples of pre-mixed components. This approach would be expected in
4 fact to encourage the production of kinetically-trapped aggregates in the samples,³⁴⁻³⁵ which
5 is intentional, as rather than to resolve the equilibrium properties, our approach is provide a
6 bridge between the fundamental studies on dilute systems and access the composition and
7 conditions closer to technologically-relevant mixtures.

8

9 **2. Experimental Section**

10 **2.1 Chemicals.** Ultrapure deionized water used for cleaning and solubilization had a
11 resistivity higher than 18 M Ω ·cm and a total organic content lower than 6 ppm (Younglin 370
12 Series, South Korea). PDADMAC was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany), and had
13 an average molecular weight in the 100 – 200 kDa range, and was used without further
14 purification. SLMT and perdeuterated SLMT were synthesized according to the procedure
15 described in Appendix A; for this purpose either hydrogenous lauric acid or perdeuterated
16 lauric acid (d²³-lauric acid) was used, purchased from TCI Europe (Belgium) and Cambridge
17 Isotopes (United Kingdom), respectively. Other precursors used were the sodium salt of
18 methyl-taurine (TCI Europe, Belgium) and oxallyl chloride (Acros). Hydrogenous and
19 perdeuterated SLMT were purified by recrystallization from 2-propanol. For the neutron
20 reflectometry experiments, deuterated water (D₂O, isotopic purity > 99.9 wt%) was
21 purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany).

1

2 **Scheme I.** Molecular structures of PDADMAC and SLMT with R being an hydrocarbon
 3 chain containing 11 carbon atoms. The vertical dashed lines on the surfactant show how the
 4 molecule needed to be split up into different layers for the structural analysis using neutron
 5 reflectometry.

6

7 The pH of all solutions was adjusted to 5.6 using glacial acetic acid (purity > 99 %) and the
 8 ionic strength was kept constant by adding 0.3 wt% of KCl (purity > 99.9 %). The
 9 PDADMAC concentration was kept constant at 0.5 wt% in all the samples. The SLMT
 10 concentration, [SLMT], is defined as the ratio between the mass of surfactant, m_s , and the
 11 total mass of the solution, m_T , and varies from 10^{-9} to 10^{-3} g/g.

12 **2.2. Samples preparation.** Polyelectrolyte – surfactant mixtures were prepared in all the
 13 cases by weight as it is described in the following: first the required amount of PDADMAC
 14 from an aqueous stock solution with concentration 20 wt% is poured into a flask to prepare
 15 final solutions with polymer concentration of 0.5 wt%. Afterwards the required amount of the
 16 KCl is added until to reach a salt concentration in the final sample of 0.3 wt%. The last step

PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 involves the addition of the surfactant solution (pH ~ 5.6) and the final dilution with acetic
2 acid solution of pH ~ 5.6 to reach the desired bulk compositions. In all the cases, the added
3 surfactant solution presents a SLMT concentration, in g/g, one order of magnitude higher
4 than that required in the final sample. The addition of the different component was performed
5 without any delay time between the addition of the different components. Once the samples
6 were prepared, they were mixed by mild stirring (1000 rpm) using a magnetic stirrer during
7 one hour. This procedure inevitably produced kinetically-trapped aggregates during the initial
8 mixing, and their persistent after dilution as well as their effects on the interfacial properties
9 are discussed. In order to ensure reproducibility in the results all the samples were aged
10 during one week before they were used in measurements.

11 2.3 Techniques

12 a. Surface tension measurements

13 The surface tension of SLMT and PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures was measured against the
14 bulk surfactant concentration using different tensiometric techniques and tensiometers. The
15 adsorption at the water / vapor interface was measured until steady state was reached, i.e.
16 changes of surface tension smaller than $0.1 \text{ mN}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ during 30 minutes. Special care was
17 taken to minimize evaporation effects. For this purpose, the different tensiometers were
18 mounted inside a closed methacrylate box with high relative humidity obtained using open
19 flasks containing saturated solutions of K_2SO_4 . In addition, whenever possible, special closed
20 cells were used. All experiments were carried out at $25.0 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$.

21 a.1. Surface force tensiometers. A surface force tensiometer from Krüss K10 (Germany) was
22 first used with different types of Pt contact probes: a Wilhelmy plate and a de Nöuy ring.
23 Special care was taken for the cleaning of the Pt probes, which were burned after each
24 experiment to ensure the removal of any sign of organic materials that could be adsorbed
PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 onto its surface as any adsorption would modify plate wettability thus reducing the reliability
2 of the results.

3 Additionally, a surface force tensiometer from Nima Technology (United Kingdom) was used
4 with disposable paper plates (Whatman CHR1 chromatography paper), ensuring a zero
5 contact angle. A new paper plate was used for each measurement to avoid potential
6 modifications on the plate surface due to the adsorption of material.

7 Each reported experimental data point was the average of at least three independent
8 measurements. The precision of γ was $\pm 2 \text{ mN}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$. The time of the experiments was long
9 enough to ensure that steady state had been reached.

10 *a.2. Shape profile analysis tensiometer.* The surface tension of PDADMAC – SLMT
11 mixtures at the water / vapor interface was also measured using a home-made profile
12 analysis.^{46, 52} Samples were measured using a pendant drop. In addition, some samples were
13 measured using a bubble configuration. It is important to keep in mind that while the drop
14 hangs in air, the bubble is surrounded by a much larger volume of the solution.

15 *b. Brewster Angle Microscopy*

16 Brewster Angle Microscopy (BAM) images were obtained with an EP³-Imaging Ellipsometer
17 from Nanofilm (Germany) at an angle of 53.1° and using a Nd-YAG laser (50 mW) with $\lambda =$
18 532 nm. Images collected through a 10x objective (Nikon, Japan) were collected using a
19 CCD camera. Before each measurement the focus was corrected automatically using a
20 software controlled objective. The height of the interface was modified manually to ensure
21 that the images were obtained directly from the interface.

22 *c. Neutron reflectometry*

PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 Neutron reflectometry experiments were carried out using the time-of-flight horizontal
 2 reflectometer FIGARO at the Institut Laue-Langevin (ILL, Grenoble, France).⁵³ The neutron
 3 reflectivity profiles of $\log_{10}R(Q)$ were recorded in the range of wavelengths $\lambda = 2 - 30 \text{ \AA}$ to
 4 ensure good overlap between the data measured at incident angles $\theta = 0.622^\circ$ and 3.78° ,
 5 where R is the measured reflectivity and $Q = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \sin \theta$ is the momentum transfer in the range
 6 $0.005 - 0.4 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$. Data were normalized with reference to a measurement of pure D_2O . The
 7 analysis was carried out using Motorfit,⁵⁴ which is based on the application of an optical
 8 matrix model based on Abele's formulism⁵⁵ to the experimental data. Mixtures of
 9 PDADMAC with deuterated surfactant were measured in pure D_2O and in air contrast
 10 matched water (ACMW), which is a mixture of 8.1% v/v D_2O in H_2O to give zero scattering
 11 length density. Two different data analysis approaches were used.

12 First, a direct measure of the SLMT surface excess (Γ_s) in 10 mixtures was performed by
 13 fitting the scattering excess at low- Q values ($0.01 - 0.03 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$) of data recorded in only the
 14 isotopic contrast involving ACMW. Background was not subtracted from the data. In this
 15 case, the contribution from the polyelectrolyte was neglected as the scattering length of one
 16 of its monomer unit ($b_P = 2.7 \text{ fm}$) is negligible compared with that of one deuterated
 17 surfactant molecule ($b_S = 262 \text{ fm}$). In this model, the layer thickness (d) was fitted with an
 18 arbitrary scattering length density of $\sigma = 3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ \AA}^{-2}$, fixed roughness values of 4 \AA , and a
 19 background of 5.65×10^{-5} fitted from measurements of pure ACMW. The following equation
 20 was then solved:

$$21 \quad \Gamma = \frac{\sigma d}{b_S N_A} \quad (1)$$

22 where N_A is Avogadro's number.

1 Second, a structural analysis was carried out by applying a consistent physical model to data
 2 recorded in both isotopic contrasts over the whole accessible Q-range. The two isotopic
 3 contrasts were chosen because the one in ACMW is most sensitive to the amount of
 4 surfactant and the one in D₂O is most sensitive to the amount of polyelectrolyte. Background
 5 was subtracted from the data using the area detector. In a first step, data of pure deuterated
 6 SLMT at its critical micelle concentration were fitted using a three-layer model
 7 corresponding to the divisions on the molecule marked in scheme 1. While it is not common
 8 to have to split the surfactant into 3 layers, the necessity for this arises because of the sharp
 9 variations in scattering length density along the length of the molecule: the first portion with
 10 deuterated chains has a high scattering length density ($6.8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ \AA}^{-2}$), the second portion
 11 with the organic part of the head group has a low scattering length density ($0.28 \times 10^{-6} \text{ \AA}^{-2}$),
 12 and the third portion with the ionic part of the head group has an intermediate scattering
 13 length density ($3.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ \AA}^{-2}$). As such, a two-layer model was inadequate to fit the data.
 14 The thickness of the chains layer was fitted with a volume fraction of 1, and in order to
 15 conserve the same number of the parts of the surfactant molecules the volume fractions of the
 16 two head group layers ($\phi_{2,3}$), each fixed at a thickness of 3 Å, were constrained according to

$$17 \quad \phi_{2,3} = \frac{\sigma_1 d_1 b_{2,3}}{\sigma_{2,3} d_{2,3} b_1} \quad (2)$$

18 Fixed roughness values of 4 Å and a residual background of 3×10^{-7} were used. In a second
 19 step, data of PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures were fitted where polyelectrolyte was
 20 incorporated into the lower head group layer in contact with the solvent. Other structural
 21 models were attempted but this one gave the best fits to the data. In this case, the thicknesses
 22 of the chains and lower head group layers were fitted, the volume fraction of the upper head
 23 group layer was constrained according to eq. 2, and the volume fraction of the lower head

PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 group layer was constrained again so that there was a consistent number of each part of the
 2 surfactant molecule according to

$$3 \quad \varphi_3 = \frac{\sigma_1 d_1 b_3 (\sigma_{\text{heads},3} - \sigma_{\text{poly}})}{\sigma_3 d_3 b_1 (\sigma_{\text{fitted},3} - \sigma_{\text{poly}})} \quad (3)$$

4 The fitted surfactant surface excesses resulting from the two data analysis approaches were in
 5 good agreement as is demonstrated below.

6 *d. Electrophoretic mobility measurements*

7 Electrophoretic mobility, μ_e , measurements were carried out using a Zetasizer Nano ZS
 8 instrument (Malvern Instruments Ltd., Worcestershire, UK).

9 *e. Turbidimetry*

10 The turbidity of the samples was determined by measuring the transmittance of the mixtures
 11 at 400 nm using a UV/visible spectrophotometer (HP-UV 8452). The turbidity is represented
 12 as $(100-T (\%))/100$, with T being the transmittance.

13

14 **3. Results and discussion**

15 **3.1. Adsorption of the pure components at the water / vapor interface**

16 Understanding the adsorption of PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures at the water / vapor interface
 17 requires a previous understanding of the adsorption of the two components separately. Figure
 18 1 shows the surface tension isotherms obtained for the adsorption of PDADMAC and SLMT
 19 separately at different bulk concentrations (note that all solutions were made in 0.3 wt% of
 20 KCl at pH 5.6).

PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 There is a negligible adsorption of PDADMAC at the water / vapor interface, as γ is
 2 equivalent to the value of pure water over the whole concentration range studied. These
 3 results are in good agreement with the results by Noskov et al.⁵⁶ who showed that
 4 PDADMAC is not surface active for concentrations lower than 3 wt%. For SLMT, γ
 5 decreases as the bulk surfactant concentration increases until the concentration overcomes the
 6 critical micellar concentration (cmc). The surface tension values for the deuterated SLMT
 7 coincide with those of its hydrogenous analogue (data not shown).

8
 9 **Figure 1.** Surface tension dependence on PDADMAC concentration for pure PDADMAC
 10 solutions (top axis, ▲). The line is a guide for the eyes. Surface tension dependence on
 11 SLMT concentration (bottom axis) for pure SLMT solutions as was obtained using a
 12 Wilhelmy plate tensiometer with a Pt probe (○) and a drop shape analysis tensiometer (■).
 13 The solid line represents the best fit of the experimental isotherms to Frumkin isotherms,
 14 whereas the dotted line represents the region of quasi-constant surface tension once the cmc
 15 is overcome.

PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1

2 The γ data obtained with the different tensiometers agree with each other within the
 3 combined errors, although the results of the drop shape tensiometer are slightly higher than
 4 those of the Pt Wilhelmy plate tensiometer. This can be understood in terms of the partial
 5 depletion of surfactant from the bulk due to the adsorption at the interface. The depletion is
 6 important in drop profile analysis tensiometer experiments because the ratio of the interfacial
 7 area to the drop volume is much higher than for the Pt Wilhelmy plate tensiometer. This
 8 surfactant depletion in the drop has also been discussed very recently by Fainerman et al.⁵⁷
 9 Therefore, a slight depletion of the bulk concentration associated with the surfactant
 10 adsorption at the interface will present a more critical effect in the case of the drop
 11 measurements. It is worth mentioning that surface tension measurements provide a value of
 12 the cmc about 2×10^{-4} g/g for SLMT. The experimental isotherm for SLMT (see Figure 1)
 13 can be described using the Frumkin isotherm defined as³⁷

$$14 \quad bc = \frac{\Gamma \omega}{1 - \Gamma \omega} e^{-2a\Gamma \omega} \quad (4)$$

$$15 \quad -\frac{\Pi \omega}{RT} = \ln(1 - \Gamma \omega) + a(\Gamma \omega)^2 \quad (5)$$

16 where c is the bulk concentration whereas Γ is referred to the surface excess, ω is the area of
 17 a molecule in the close packed monolayer, b corresponds to the constant of the adsorption
 18 equilibrium, a is the parameter of molecular interaction, and R and T are the gas constant and
 19 the absolute temperature, respectively. Table 1 summarizes the parameters for the best fit to
 20 the Frumkin model of the combined data obtained by both tensiometers used.

21 **Table 1.** Parameters obtained from the best fit of the experimental isotherm for SLMT to a
 22 Frumkin model (Figure 1)

$10^{-2} \cdot b$ (l/mmol)

$10^{-5} \cdot \omega$ (m²/mol)

a

PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1.36

3.26

1.32

1

2 **3.2. Interactions of PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures in the bulk solution**

3 A necessary first step before a study of the adsorption of PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures at
 4 fluid interfaces is an analysis of the charge of the formed complexes and an examination of
 5 any aggregation that takes place in the bulk. Figure 2 shows the dependence of the
 6 electrophoretic mobility and turbidity on the bulk surfactant concentration.

7

8 **Figure 2.** SLMT concentration dependences of the turbidity (left axis, ▲) and electrophoretic
 9 mobility (right axis, ○) for PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures. The solid line is referred to the
 10 electrophoretic mobility value of PDADMAC. The results correspond to samples aged during
 11 one week.

12

13 The results of the electrophoretic mobility show positive values, close to that corresponding
 14 to the polyelectrolyte, over the entire range of bulk surfactant concentrations studied. Thus, it
 15 is possible to infer that the samples all contain complexes with excess polyelectrolyte

PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 segments. This finding can be rationalized with reference to the efficient binding and low free
2 surfactant concentration at charge neutralization (~ 0.2 mM) for 100 ppm PDADMAC – SDS
3 mixtures.^{17,18} If one neglects any differences in the binding isotherm from the change of
4 surfactant structure and higher ionic strength, and if little variation in the free surfactant
5 concentration at charge neutralization is assumed with changing bulk polyelectrolyte
6 concentration, a simple extrapolation of the bulk polyelectrolyte concentration by a factor of
7 50 would put charge neutralization at a higher bulk surfactant concentration than the samples
8 measured in Figure 2. Hence it follows that the complexes in all the samples measured are in
9 the undercharged regime.

10 This scenario indicates that all the mixtures studied fall in an equilibrium one-phase region
11 where freshly mixed samples are expected to be optically transparent. Nevertheless, at
12 compositions close to the phase boundary, kinetically-trapped particles can be produced
13 during mixing, and this results in turbid samples.³³ Therefore it is helpful to examine the
14 phase behavior of the samples by carrying out turbidity measurements. Only for the higher
15 bulk SLMT concentrations studied, there is the onset of phase separation as evidenced by the
16 increase of the turbidity. This is an essential difference in relation to many studies on more
17 dilute systems in the literature, in which the surface tension dependence on the bulk
18 surfactant concentration covered a transition from undercharged through neutral to
19 overcharged complexes.^{21-22,24,25, 58} As there is no indication of the approach of charge
20 neutralization of the bulk complexes from the electrophoretic measurements measurements in
21 the samples in Figure 2, we may infer that the turbidity arises from the presence of
22 kinetically-trapped aggregates that were produced as the components were mixed then diluted
23 to the stated bulk composition.³⁴⁻³⁵

24

25 **3.3. Adsorption of PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures at the water / vapor interface**

PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

- 1 Measurements performed using different tensiometers can help to shed light on the complex
- 2 interfacial behavior present in oppositely charged polyelectrolyte – surfactant solutions.
- 3 Figure 3a shows the surface tension obtained by a drop shape tensiometer. For the sake of
- 4 comparison the data corresponding to the SLMT is also included.

- 5
 - 6 **Figure 3.** (a) Surface tension dependences on SLMT concentration for PDADMAC – SLMT
 - 7 mixed solutions and pure SLMT solutions measured with a drop shape tensiometer. (b)
 - 8 Surface tension dependences on the bulk SLMT concentration for PDADMAC – SLMT
- PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 mixtures obtained using five different tensiometers. The errors bars were calculated as the
2 standard deviation of the results obtained from three independent measurements. The results
3 correspond to samples aged during one week.

4
5 For the lowest bulk surfactant concentrations measured, the behavior is similar for both
6 pure SLMT and PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures, so it could be assumed that only a low
7 coverage of molecules adsorb at the fluid interface. The surface concentration is not
8 enough to lower the free energy of the interface, thus the surface tension remains close to
9 the value corresponding to pure water. An increase of the bulk SLMT concentration leads
10 to a monotonic lowering of γ for the mixtures, with the decrease equivalent for bulk
11 surfactant concentrations about one order of magnitude lower than for the pure surfactant.
12 This type of behavior has been previously reported for the adsorption of other polymer –
13 surfactant mixtures at the water / vapor interface.^{4, 21-22, 24-25, 59}

14 The data and physical description above do not include any non-regular trends in the surface
15 tension isotherms. In contrast, Figure 3b shows that different results were obtained when
16 different tensiometers were used. Fluctuations in the data are evident only when Wilhelmy
17 plate tensiometer with Pt probe was used. Such a type of discrepancy between the results
18 obtained using different techniques has been previously reported by Noskov et al.⁶⁰ This
19 behavior was explained in terms of the following considerations: a) the aggregation kinetics
20 of polyelectrolyte – surfactant complexes in the bulk, and b) the differences on the physical
21 bases of the different techniques.

22 As already mentioned, oppositely charged polyelectrolyte – surfactant mixtures are systems
23 that are often dominated by non-equilibrium effects related to the production of kinetically-
24 trapped aggregates during mixing of the components.³⁴⁻³⁵ The resulting direct effects on the

PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 interfacial properties have also been characterized, as it has been shown that fluctuations in
2 the amount of material at the interface of a polyelectrolyte – surfactant mixture were evident
3 in samples more than three orders of magnitude in bulk composition from the equilibrium
4 two-phase region,²⁷ and that such kinetically-trapped aggregates could be visualized using
5 BAM.²⁶ Thus, to examine if the appearance of the surface tension fluctuations in PDADMAC
6 – SLMT mixtures for the measurements carried out using the Wilhelmy plate tensiometer
7 with a Pt probe may be associated with the formation of aggregates that can be trapped at the
8 interface and consequently adsorbed onto the Pt probe, we studied the system using BAM
9 (see Figure 4a and 4b). It can be seen that there are aggregates that have coalesced laterally to
10 form isolated islands. As such, given the inhomogeneity in the lateral morphology, to a first
11 approximation one may assume that their effect on the surface tension might be minimal.
12 Recent work on related systems has shown how polyelectrolyte – surfactant aggregates can
13 dissociate and spread material by Marangoni flow across the liquid / vapor interface in the
14 form of a kinetically-trapped film that can lower the surface tension, but this work was
15 conducted on a pure water subphase without a substantial excess of one component in the
16 bulk.²⁴ Even so, the aggregates trapped at the interface at bulk compositions far from the
17 equilibrium two-phase region, as imaged using BAM, do coincide with the non-monotonic
18 surface tension behavior from the Wilhelmy plate tensiometer with a Pt probe, hence the
19 issue merits further consideration.

20 The question is then raised why surface tension fluctuations were observed only using this
21 particular tensiometric technique. We may reason that the trapped, hydrophobic PDADMAC
22 – SLMT aggregates can stick more readily onto the rough planar Pt probe surface, thus
23 changing the contact angle of the Pt plate with the interface, and consequently the value of
24 the surface tension determined using this technique is affected (this adsorption can be the
25 origin of the changes on the contact angle of water drops found for the clean plate and the
PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 plate after the measurements). If this physical picture were correct, to a first approximation an
2 analogous effect using the Pt De Nouy ring could be expected. However, the smaller surface
3 area in contact with the solutions and the fact that it is not rough make the sticking of
4 aggregates less favorable, and consequently the modification of the contact angle, thus
5 providing surface tension values that are monotonic. The absence of surface tension
6 fluctuations was also found when other tensiometric techniques were used. This observation
7 confirms that the trapped aggregates do not spontaneously dissociate to spread a kinetically-
8 trapped film at the interface of solutions with such a large excess of polyelectrolyte (and
9 counterions) in the bulk. When a paper probe was used the solution wets the plate completely
10 and any possible effect of aggregates sticking is much smaller, and in the case of drop or
11 bubble shape tensiometers there is no equivalent probe so there is no such effect. The
12 irregular large aggregates at the water / vapor interface are mostly observed at the lower bulk
13 SLMT concentrations examined (Figure 4a and 4b). At higher bulk SLMT concentrations, the
14 aggregates are smaller and more homogeneous in appearance (Figure 4c and 4d). This
15 observation is consistent with the results by Monteux et al.⁶¹ on the poly(sodium styrene
16 sulfonate) – dodecyltrimethylammonium bromide system.

1

2 **Figure 4.** BAM images of the lateral morphology of PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures at the
 3 water / vapor interface at different values of the bulk SLMT concentration: a) 10^{-9} . b) 10^{-8} .
 4 c) 10^{-7} . d) 10^{-6} g/g. The dimensions of the images are $438 \times 320 \mu\text{m}^2$. The results
 5 correspond to samples aged during one week.

6

7 There is one additional difference between the data on PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures
 8 recorded using the different tensiometric techniques, one that is systematic rather than
 9 random in nature: the data measured using the pendant drop is shifted to higher bulk SLMT
 10 concentrations. Discrepancies between the results obtained using drop and bubble profile
 11 analysis tensiometers have been found in previous studies.^{46, 62-63} Furthermore, previous
 12 studies on the adsorption of proteins have evidenced that the results obtained using bubble
 13 profile tensiometers agree well with those results obtained by Wilhelmy plate tensiometer.⁴⁴
 14 The differences in the isotherms associated with different configurations of analysis profile
 15 tensiometer (drop and bubble) can be explained taking into account the different relation
 PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 between the surface area of the interface and the volume of the solution containing the
2 polyelectrolyte – surfactant mixture. In the case of pendant drop configuration, the adsorption
3 at the surface of the drop leads to a decrease of the effective concentration of the sample
4 solution, i.e., a depletion effect. Thus, the lower volume of the drop in comparison with its
5 surface area leads to a significant decrease of the effective concentration of the bulk, leading
6 to higher values of the surface tension. On the other hand, if the bubble configuration is used,
7 the depletion effect is not observed since the adsorbed amount is negligible in relation to the
8 total concentration of surface-active material in the sample. The same explanation based on
9 the ratio interfacial area / volume of the sample can be used for explaining the discrepancies
10 found between the experiments performed using the drop shape tensiometer, and those
11 obtained using the contact plate/ring probes. The differences associated with the depletion of
12 material in profile analysis tensiometers are schematized in Figure 5.

13
14 **Figure 5.** Schematic representation of the adsorption of surfactant molecules and polymer –
15 surfactant complexes to the water / vapor interface and the different phenomena that take
16 place depending on the technique used: profile analysis tensiometer in drop configuration
17 (left panel) and in bubble configuration (right panel).

18

1 The analysis of the differences between the results obtained for tensiometric techniques
 2 involving a different surface area / volume ratio can provide an estimation of the surface
 3 excess according to the approximation proposed by Fainerman et al.⁵⁷ However, such an
 4 approximation is developed for single-component systems, whereas in our case we are
 5 dealing with polyelectrolyte – surfactant mixtures. Thus, it is necessary to analyze the degree
 6 of binding between the surfactant molecules and the polymer monomers before a calculation
 7 of the surface concentration on the basis of the model proposed by Fainerman et al.⁵⁷ Figure 6
 8 shows the dependence of the binding degree $\beta = c_s^{free} / c_{monomer}$, with c_s^{free} being the
 9 concentration of free surfactant and $c_{monomer}$ the concentration of charged monomers units of
 10 the polyelectrolyte, as obtained by potentiometric measurements carried out using surfactant
 11 selective electrode.

12
 13 **Figure 6.** Surface excess obtained from eq. 5 (solid line) and surface excess of SLMT
 14 (symbols) as was obtained by neutron reflectometry. Note that the error bars are smaller than
 15 the data size for the data from neutron reflectometry (left axis, black triangles). Binding
 16 isotherm of SLMT on PDADMAC as function of the initial SLMT bulk concentration (right
 PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 axis, white circles). The line is a guide for the eyes. The results correspond to samples aged
 2 during one week.

3

4 The binding isotherm evidences a high degree of binding of the surfactant molecules to the
 5 polyelectrolyte molecules in the bulk over a broad range of the bulk composition measured.

6 Again, with reference to previous work conducted on much more dilute PDADMAC – SDS
 7 mixtures in 0.1 M NaCl,²⁴⁻²⁵ and again for simplicity neglecting the difference in the structure
 8 of the surfactant and ionic strength, for 100 ppm the binding degree at charge neutralization is
 9 ~ 0.3, so an extrapolation of the bulk polyelectrolyte concentration by a factor of 50 without
 10 major changes in c_s^{free} places the binding degree at charge neutralization as < 1 %. As all the
 11 samples measured in the present study have a much lower bulk surfactant concentrations than
 12 charge neutralization and therefore contain undercharged complexes, this would put the
 13 binding degree at << 1 %. Indeed the results reveal a very low binding degree, as only around
 14 3 % of the surfactant molecules in the PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures remain free even for
 15 the highest concentrations. As a result of this very low binding degree, if we were to make an
 16 approximation of zero free surfactant, we could use the surface tension isotherm to estimate
 17 the total surfactant surface excess as⁵⁷

$$18 \quad \Gamma = \frac{V_d}{A_d} (c_d - c_b)_\gamma \quad (6)$$

19 where $(c_d - c_b)_\gamma$ is the difference in bulk surfactant concentration for a fixed value of
 20 surface tension between the concentration on the drop and the bubble experiments, V_d is
 21 the volume of the drop and A_d the area of the drop. Figure 6 shows the surface excess
 22 calculated according eq. 6 and the surface excess of surfactant measured directly using
 PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 neutron reflectometry (see first analysis method in the Experimental Section).

2 The experimental results and the one obtained on the bases of eq. 6 shows a monotonic
3 increase of the surface excess with the surfactant concentration. However, the experimental
4 and calculated values coincide only for the lowest bulk SLMT concentration, where indeed
5 the binding degree is expected to be lowest. This suggests that the complexity of the system
6 at higher bulk surfactant concentrations, where the free surfactant concentration cannot be
7 neglected, requires the development of complex thermodynamic multi-component models
8 that account for the differences on the activities of the different component involved.

9 In order to deepen our understanding of the composition of the interface, additional neutron
10 reflectometry experiments were carried out. Figure 7 shows an example of data recorded over
11 the whole accessible Q-range in two isotopic contrasts as well as fits using the three-layer
12 model for samples with a bulk SLMT concentration of 3×10^{-6} g/g (see second analysis
13 method in the Experimental Section). The inset shows the scattering length density profiles in
14 the two isotopic contrasts with respect to the distance from the interface. Here, effectively the
15 area of the peak in the blue curve is related to the amount of surfactant at the interface, and
16 the area of the inflexion of the green curve is related the corresponding amount of
17 polyelectrolyte. Figure 8 shows the resulting surface excesses of PDADMAC and SLMT
18 obtained from this structural analysis in addition to the 10 SLMT surface excesses in the
19 mixtures repeated from Figure 6.

1

2 **Figure 7.** Neutron reflectivity profiles of PDADMAC – SLMT mixtures with a bulk
 3 SLMT concentration of 3×10^{-6} g/g. The isotopic contrasts involve deuterated surfactant
 4 in ACMW (blue) and in D₂O (green). The model fits are shown as lines. The inset shows
 5 the scattering length density (SLD) profiles in the two isotopic contrasts with respect to
 6 the distance from the interface. **The results correspond to samples aged during one week.**

1
 2 **Figure 8.** Surface excesses of PDADMAC (□) and SLMT (■) in 5 of their mixtures from the
 3 structural analysis, and surface excess of SLMT (▲, same results reported in Figure 6) in 10
 4 of their mixtures from the low-Q analysis, both determined using neutron reflectometry. **The**
 5 **results correspond to samples aged during one week.**

6
 7
 8 The results show that both methodologies to obtain the surface excess of the surfactant are in
 9 good agreement. The use of the structural analysis to determine the amount of PDADMAC at
 10 the interface reveals an interesting trend. At low bulk SLMT concentrations, there is a large
 11 excess of polyelectrolyte segments at the interface as the polyelectrolyte surface excess (in
 12 monomer units) is three times that of the surfactant. However, as the bulk SLMT
 PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 concentration increases, the interfacial stoichiometry reaches unity by 10^{-5} g/g, and at the
2 highest bulk SLMT concentration measure the surfactant surface excess exceeds that of the
3 polyelectrolyte by $\sim 15\%$.

4 A first interpretation of this trend in the interfacial composition is that qualitatively it mirrors
5 the changes in bulk composition, and that an adequate physical framework to describe the
6 interfacial properties of these samples in the semi-dilute regime, where the free bulk
7 surfactant concentration is relatively low, may be one of adsorption of complexes formed in
8 the bulk. This picture is in contrast to that in studies of samples with undercharged complexes
9 in the dilute regime,^{16-18,20} where there is not a significant shift in the interfacial composition
10 with changing bulk composition, which can be attributed to the synergistic co-adsorption of
11 free surfactant with the complexes. The large excess of polyelectrolyte at the interface in the
12 sample with 10^{-7} g/g SLMT can be rationalized by the very low free surfactant concentration
13 as a result of the high polyelectrolyte concentration used (see Figure 6). Even so, the
14 complexes are positive charged in all of the samples measured (see Figure 1), and therefore to
15 achieve equimolar binding with a bulk SLMT concentration of 10^{-5} g/g, there must be co-
16 adsorption with additional surfactant adsorbed at the interface. This strong effect is evident
17 even though $\sim 97\%$ of the surfactant is bound in complexes with the polyelectrolyte, which
18 underlines the important role of a rather small amount of the free surfactant in determining
19 the interfacial properties of these mixtures. The observed transition between the regimes of
20 complex adsorption and synergistic co-adsorption is clearly an interesting facet of the
21 behavior of the more concentrated samples studied in the present work. This issue merits
22 further investigation in a range of technologically-realistic systems in the future, both in
23 terms of additional components and the behaviour of the systems under dynamic conditions
24 involving flow.

PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1

2 **4. Conclusions**

3 Our study on the adsorption of mixtures of polyelectrolytes and surfactants bearing
4 opposite charges at the water / vapor interface, involving a bulk polyelectrolyte
5 concentration close to that used in commercial formulations, has evidenced important
6 differences in relation to the numerous studies of more dilute systems. The main origin of
7 this difference lies in the fact that over the range of bulk surfactant concentrations
8 measured, there is a very low free surfactant concentration. This means that a physical
9 framework involving the adsorption of bulk complexes becomes more relevant than in
10 systems with lower bulk polyelectrolyte concentrations in which a framework of
11 synergistic co-adsorption of complexes and free surfactant is more appropriate.
12 Nevertheless, there is stoichiometric binding at the interface even at a bulk compositions
13 far from stoichiometric binding in the bulk, which demonstrates that this synergistic
14 effect can dominate the interfacial behavior even in these more concentrated mixtures
15 when the free surfactant concentration is on the order of just a few percent.

16 At the same time, even though the samples in the present work existed in an equilibrium
17 one-phase region, and their optical density when freshly mixed remained low except for
18 those with the highest bulk surfactant concentrations measured, the effects of kinetically-
19 trapped aggregates on the interfacial properties were extensive. Our applied mixing
20 protocol of the components (i.e. mix concentrated components then dilute) was
21 deliberately crude in order to mimick the type of stepwise processes used in industrial
22 plants. The resulting particles were imaged at the vapor / air interface at bulk
23 compositions that were several orders of magnitude from the equilibrium two-phase
24 region, and the relatively large size of the islands observed pointed to lateral coalescence
PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 of the aggregates at the interface. Further, depending on the tensiometric technique
2 applied, fluctuations were observed in the surface tension isotherm, which was attributed
3 to attachment of the aggregates to the probe. This evidence may help to rationalize some
4 of the numerous discrepancies in the literature from different tensiometric techniques
5 applied to mixed systems.

6 The main novelty of this work is related to the fact that the system studied is closer not
7 only in composition but also sample history to those used in real technological
8 applications. Thus this information on the interfacial behavior can help to improve our
9 understanding of the physico-chemical bases underlying the performance of
10 polyelectrolyte – surfactant systems in applications involving detergency or foam
11 stabilization. On the basis of this work, it will be important to continue this direction
12 towards mixtures involving a greater a number of components and under dynamic
13 conditions of flow in order to make further steps to a coherent understanding of more
14 relevant mixtures under more realistic conditions.

15

16 **Acknowledgements**

17 This work was funded in part by MINECO under grants FIS 2014-62005-EXP and CTQ-
18 2016- 78895-R, by EU under Marie Curie ITN CoWet (Grant Number 607861). This work is
19 based upon work from COST Action MP-1305. The authors are grateful to the CAI of
20 Espectroscopia y Correlación of UCM for the use of their facilities and to the ILL for an
21 allocation of neutron beam time on FIGARO as well as the Partnership for Soft Condensed
22 Matter for access to ancillary equipment during the experiment.

23

PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1

2

3 **Appendix A**

4 **A.1. Synthesis of lauroyl chloride.**

5 To a solution of lauric acid (5 g, 25 mmol) in anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ (50 mL) under Ar DMF (50
6 μl) was added followed by a 2 M solution of oxalyl chloride in CH₂Cl₂ (37.4 mL, 75 mmol).

7 The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h, and then at 40°C for 3 h. Volatiles were
8 removed under reduced pressure, leaving an oily residue (crude lauroyl chloride, pale yellow
9 oil) which was used in the next step without further purification.

10

11 **A.2. Synthesis of sodium N-lauroyl-N-methyltaurate.**

12 To a stirred solution of sodium *N*-methyltaurate (4.0 g, 25 mmol) in water (20 mL) at 10-
13 15°C under Ar, crude lauroyl chloride (25 mmol) and sodium hydroxide (1.0 g dissolved in
14 1.6 mL of water) were simultaneously added over 4 h while maintaining the pH at ~10. The
15 reaction mixture was then allowed to stir overnight at room temperature. Water was added
16 (10 mL, final pH ~ 9), and the solution was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 20 mL). The
17 aqueous layer was treated with 1 M HCl to reach pH ~ 5, and extracted with ethyl acetate (3
18 × 20 mL). Finally, the aqueous layer was treated with 6 M NaOH to reach pH ~ 14, and
19 extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 20 mL). The aqueous layer was deposited in an Erlenmeyer
20 flask and was allowed to crystallize overnight. The white solid was filtered and recrystallized
21 from isopropanol to afford sodium *N*-lauroyl-*N*-methyltaurate (4.8 g, 56%). ¹H-NMR (300
22 MHz, DMSO-d₆, 1:1 mixture of amide rotamers, Figure A.1a) δ 0.85 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 3H), 1.24
23 (m, 16H), 1.45 (m, 2H), 2.18-2.29 (m, 2H), 2.57-2.66 (m, 2H), 2.74 (s, 3H, rotamer A), 2.91
24 (s, 3H, rotamer B), 3.44-3.52 (m, 2H) ppm. ¹³C-NMR (75 MHz, MeOH-d₄, 1:1 mixture of
PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

1 amide rotamers, Figure A2) δ 14.5 (CH₃), 23.8 (CH₂), 26.2 (CH₂), 26.7 (CH₂), 30.5 (CH₂),
 2 30.6 (CH₂), 30.7 (CH₂), 30.8 (CH₂), 33.1 (CH₂), 33.8 (CH₃), 33.9 (CH₂), 34.5, (CH₂), 36.7
 3 (CH₃), 45.5 (CH₂), 47.2 (CH₂), 49.3 (CH₂), 49.9 (CH₃), 50.3 (CH₂), 175.9 (C), 176.2 (C)
 4 ppm. ESI (negative mode) m/z = 320.1890 (calc. for C₁₅H₃₀NO₄S, m/z = 320.1896).

5

6 **A.3. Synthesis of sodium N-d₂₃-lauroyl-N-methyltaurate.**

7 A similar procedure was followed, using d₂₃-dodecanoic acid as starting material. ¹H-NMR
 8 (300 MHz, DMSO, Figure A.1b) δ 2.57-2.66 (m, 2H), 2.84 (s, 3H), 3.44-3.52 (m, 2H) ppm.

9 ESI (negative mode) m/z = 320.1940 (calc. for C₁₅H₃₀NO₄S, m/z = 320.1946). ESI (negative

10 mode) m/z = 343.3344 (calc. for C₁₅H₇D₂₃NO₄S, m/z = 320.3339).

11

12 **Figure A.1.** ¹H-NMR spectra (300 MHz) for hydrogenous (a) and deuterated (b) SLMT
 13 obtained in d₆-DMSO and DMSO, respectively.

1

2 **Figure A.2.** ^{13}C -NMR spectra (75 MHz) for hydrogenous SLMT obtained in d_4 -MeOH.

3

4 **ReferencesUncategorized References**

- 5 1. Piculell, L.; Lindman, B., Association and Segregation in Aqueous Polymer/Polymer,
6 Polymer/Surfactant, and Surfactant/Surfactant Mixtures: Similarities and Differences. *Adv.*
7 *Colloid Interface Sci.* **1992**, *41*, 149-178. doi: 10.1016/0001-8686(92)80011-1.
- 8 2. Llamas, S.; Guzmán, E.; Ortega, F.; Baghdadli, N.; Cazeneuve, C.; Rubio, R. G.;
9 Luengo, G. S., Adsorption of polyelectrolytes and polyelectrolytes-surfactant mixtures at
10 surfaces: a physico-chemical approach to a cosmetic challenge. *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.*
11 **2015**, *222*, 461-487. doi: 10.1016/j.cis.2014.05.007.
- 12 3. Goddard, E. D., Polymer/Surfactant Interaction: Interfacial Aspects. *J. Colloid*
13 *Interface Sci.* **2002**, *256*, 228-235. doi: 10.1006/jcis.2001.8066.
- 14 4. Bain, C. D.; Claesson, P. M.; Langevin, D.; Meszaros, R.; Nylander, T.; Stubenrauch,
15 C.; Titmuss, S.; von Klitzing, R., Complexes of surfactants with oppositely charged polymers
16 at surfaces and in bulk. *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2010**, *155*, 32-49. doi:
17 10.1016/j.cis.2010.01.007.
- 18 5. Guzmán, E.; Llamas, S.; Maestro, A.; Fernández-Peña, L.; Akanno, A.; Miller, R.;
19 Ortega, F.; Rubio, R. G., Polymer-surfactant systems in bulk and at fluid interfaces. *Adv.*
20 *Colloid Interface Sci.* **2016**, *233*, 38-64. doi:10.1016/j.cis.2015.11.001.
- 21 6. Goddard, E. D.; Ananthapadmanabhan, K. P., *Application of Polymer-Surfactant*
22 *Systems*. Marcel Dekker: New York, United States of America, 1998.
- 23 7. Nylander, T.; Samoshina, Y.; Lindman, B., Formation of polyelectrolyte-surfactant
24 complexes on surfaces. *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2006**, *123-126*, 105-123. doi:
25 10.1021/acs.langmuir.7b01288.
- 26 8. Holmberg, K.; Jönsson, B.; Kronberg, B.; Lindman, B., *Surfactants and Polymers in*
27 *Aqueous Solution*. John Wiley & Sons: Chichester, United Kingdom, 2002.

- 1 9. Thalberg, K.; Lindman, B., Polymer-surfactant interactions recent developments. In
2 *Interactions of Surfactants with Polymers and Proteins*, Goddard, E. D.;
3 Ananthapadmanabhan, K. P., Eds. CRC Press: Boca Raton, United States of America, 1993.
- 4 10. Von Klitzing, R., Internal Structure of polyelectrolyte multilayer assemblies. *Phys.*
5 *Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2006**, *8*, 5012-5033. doi: 10.1039/b607760a.
- 6 11. Piculell, L., Understanding and Exploiting the Phase Behavior of Mixtures of
7 Oppositely Charged Polymers and Surfactants in Water. *Langmuir* **2013**, *29*, 10313-10329.
8 doi: 10.1021/la401026j.
- 9 12. Pagac, E. S.; Prieve, D. C.; Tilton, R. D., Kinetics and Mechanism of Cationic
10 Surfactant Adsorption and Coadsorption with Cationic Polyelectrolytes at the Silica–Water
11 Interface. *Langmuir* **1998**, *14*, 2333-2342. 10.1021/la971308f.
- 12 13. Rojas, O. J.; Claesson, P. M.; Berglund, K. D.; Tilton, R. D., Coadsorption and
13 Surface Forces for Selective Surfaces in Contact with Aqueous Mixtures of Oppositely
14 Charged Surfactants and Low Charge Density Polyelectrolytes. *Langmuir* **2004**, *20*, 3221-
15 3230. doi: 10.1021/la035752w.
- 16 14. Braem, A. D.; Prieve, D. C.; Tilton, R. D., Electrostatically Tunable Coadsorption of
17 Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate and Poly(ethylene oxide)-b-poly(propylene oxide)-b-poly(ethylene
18 oxide) Triblock Copolymer to Silica. *Langmuir* **2001**, *17*, 883-890. doi: 10.1021/la0013042.
- 19 15. Berglund, K. D.; Przybycien, T. M.; Tilton, R. D., Coadsorption of Sodium Dodecyl
20 Sulfate with Hydrophobically Modified Nonionic Cellulose Polymers. 1. Role of Polymer
21 Hydrophobic Modification. *Langmuir* **2003**, *19*, 2705-2713. doi: 10.1021/la026429g.
- 22 16. Goddard, E. D.; Phillips, T. S.; Hannan, R. B., Water soluble polymer-surfactant
23 interaction - Part I. . *J. Soc. Cosmet. Chem.* **1975**, *26*, 461-475.
- 24 17. Goddard, E. D.; Hannan, R. B., Cationic polymer/anionic surfactant interactions *J.*
25 *Colloid Interface Sci.* **1976**, *55*, 73-79. doi: 10.1016/0021-9797(76)90010-2.
- 26 18. Bergeron, V.; Langevin, D.; Asnacios, A., Thin-film forces in foam films containing
27 anionic polyelectrolyte and charged surfactants. *Langmuir* **1996** *12*, 1550-1556. doi:
28 10.1016/0021-9797(76)90010-2.
- 29 19. Ritacco, H.; Albouy, P.-A.; Bhattacharyya, A.; Langevin, D., Influence of the
30 polymer backbone rigidity on polyelectrolytesurfactant complexes at the air/water interface.
31 *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2000**, *2*, 5243–5251. doi: 10.1039/b004657o.
- 32 20. Stubenrauch, C.; Albouy, P.-A.; von Klitzing, R.; Langevin, D., Polymer/surfactant
33 complexes at the water/air interface: a surface tension and x-ray reflectivity study. *Langmuir*
34 **2000**, *16*, 3206-3213. doi: 10.1016/0021-9797(76)90010-2.
- 35 21. Staples, E.; Tucker, I.; Penfold, J.; Warren, N.; Thomas, R. K.; Taylor, D. J. F.,
36 Organization of Polymer–Surfactant Mixtures at the Air–Water Interface: Sodium Dodecyl
37 Sulfate and Poly(dimethyldiallylammonium chloride). *Langmuir* **2002**, *18*, 5147-5153. doi:
38 10.1021/la020034f.
- 39 22. Taylor, D. J. F.; Thomas, R. K.; Penfold, J., The Adsorption of Oppositely Charged
40 Polyelectrolyte/Surfactant Mixtures: Neutron Reflection from Dodecyl Trimethylammonium
41 Bromide and Sodium Poly(styrene sulfonate) at the Air/Water Interface. *Langmuir* **2002**, *18*,
42 4748-4757. doi: 10.1021/la011716q.
- 43 23. Penfold, J.; Tucker, I.; Thomas, R. K.; Zhang, J., Adsorption of
44 Polyelectrolyte/Surfactant Mixtures at the Air–Solution Interface:
45 Poly(ethyleneimine)/Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate. *Langmuir* **2005**, *21*, 10061-10073. doi:
46 10.1021/la0505014.
- 47 24. Varga, I.; Campbell, R. A., General Physical Description of the Behavior of
48 Oppositely Charged Polyelectrolyte/Surfactant Mixtures at the Air/Water Interface. *Langmuir*
49 **2017**, *33*, 5915-5924. doi: 10.1021/acs.langmuir.7b01288.

PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

- 1 25. Campbell, R. A.; Angus-Smyth, A.; Arteta, M. Y.; Tonigold, K.; Nylander, T.; Varga,
2 I., New Perspective on the Cliff Edge Peak in the Surface Tension of Oppositely Charged
3 Polyelectrolyte/Surfactant Mixtures. *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2010**, *1*, 3021-3026. doi:
4 10.1021/jz101179f.
- 5 26. Campbell, R. A.; Arteta, M. Y.; Angus-Smyth, A.; Nylander, T.; Noskov, B. A.;
6 Varga, I., Direct Impact of Non-Equilibrium Aggregates on the Structure and Morphology of
7 Pdadmac/SDS Layers at the Air/Water Interface. *Langmuir* **2014**, *30*, 8664-8774. doi:
8 10.1021/la500621t.
- 9 27. Tonigold, K.; Varga, I.; Nylander, T.; Campbell, R. A., Effects of Aggregates on
10 Mixed Adsorption Layers of Poly(ethylene imine) and Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate at the
11 Air/Liquid Interface. *Langmuir* **2009**, *25*, 4036-4046. doi: 10.1021/la8028325.
- 12 28. Braun, L.; Uhlig, M.; Von Klitzing, R.; Campbell, R. A., Polymers and surfactants at
13 fluid interfaces studied with specular neutron reflectometry. *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2017**,
14 *247*, 130-148. doi: 10.1016/j.cis.2017.07.005.
- 15 29. Kogej, K.; J., S., Surfactant Binding to Polyelectrolytes. In *Surfactant Science Series*,
16 Radeva, T., Ed. Marcell Dekker Inc.: New York, 2001; Vol. 99, pp 793-827.
- 17 30. Li, D.; Kelkar, M. S.; Wagner, N. J., Phase Behavior and Molecular Thermodynamics
18 of Coacervation in Oppositely Charged Polyelectrolyte/Surfactant Systems: A Cationic
19 Polymer JR 400 and Anionic Surfactant SDS Mixture. *Langmuir* **2012**, *28*, 10348-10362.
20 doi: 10.1021/la301475s.
- 21 31. Hansson, P.; Lindman, B., Surfactant-polymer interactions. *Curr. Opin. Colloid*
22 *Interface Sci.* **1996**, *1*, 604-613. doi: 10.1016/s1359-0294(96)80098-7.
- 23 32. Bergfeldt, K.; Piculell, L.; Linse, P., Segregation and Association in Mixed Polymer
24 Solutions from Flory-Huggins Model Calculations. *J. Phys. Chem.* **1996**, *100*, 3680-3687.
25 doi: 10.1021/jp952349s.
- 26 33. Mészáros, R.; Thompson, L.; Bos, M.; Varga, I.; Gilányi, T., Interaction of sodium
27 dodecyl sulfate with polyethyleneimine: surfactant-induced polymer solution colloid
28 dispersion transition. *Langmuir* **2003**, *19*, 609-615. doi: 10.1021/la026616e.
- 29 34. Naderi, A.; Claesson, P. M.; Bergström, M.; Dedinaite, A., Trapped non-equilibrium
30 states in aqueous solutions of oppositely charged polyelectrolytes and surfactants: effects of
31 mixing protocol and salt concentration. *Colloids Surf. A* **2005**, *253*, 83-93.
32 doi:10.1016/j.colsurfa.2004.10.123.
- 33 35. Mezei, A.; Mészáros, R.; Varga, I.; Gilányi, T., Effect of Mixing on the Formation of
34 Complexes of Hyperbranched Cationic Polyelectrolytes and Anionic Surfactants. *Langmuir*
35 **2007**, *23*, 4237-4247. doi: 10.1021/la0635294.
- 36 36. Banerjee, S.; Cazeneuve, C.; Baghdadli, N.; Ringeissen, S.; Leermakers, F. A. M.;
37 Luengo, G. S., Surfactant-polymer interactions: molecular architecture does matter. *Soft*
38 *Matter* **2015**, *11*, 2504-2511. doi: 10.1039/c5sm00117j.
- 39 37. Eiseenthal, K. B., Equilibrium and dynamic processes at interfaces by second harmonic
40 and sum frequency generation. *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.* **1992**, *43*, 627-661. doi:
41 10.1146/annurev.pc.43.100192.003211
- 42 38. von Klitzing, R.; Kolaric, B.; Jaeger, W.; Brandt, A., Structuring of poly(DADMAC)
43 chains in aqueous media: a comparison between bulk and free-standing film measurements.
44 *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2002**, *4*, 1907-1914. doi: 10.1039/b106929m.
- 45 39. Goddard, E. D.; Gruber, J. V., *Principles of Polymer Science and Technology in*
46 *Cosmetics and Personal Care*. Marcel Dekker, Inc.: Basel, Switzerland, 1999.
- 47 40. Decher, G.; Schlenoff, J. B., *Multilayer Thin Films-Sequential Assembly of*
48 *Nanocomposite Materials*. Wiley-VCH Verlag: Berlin, 2003.

- 1 41. Guzmán, E.; Ritacco, H. A.; Ortega, F.; Rubio, R. G., Growth of Polyelectrolyte
2 Layers Formed by Poly(4-styrenesulfonate sodium salt) and Two Different Polycations: New
3 Insights from Study of Adsorption Kinetics. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2012**, *116*, 15474–154. doi:
4 10.1021/jp304522t.
- 5 42. Fang, J. P.; Joos, P., The Dynamic Surface Tension of SDS—Dodecanol Mixtures: 1.
6 The Submicellar Systems. *Colloids Surf. A* **1992**, *65*, 113-120. doi: 10.1016/0166-
7 6622(92)80266-5.
- 8 43. Llamas, S.; Guzmán, E.; Baghdadli, N.; Ortega, F.; Cazeneuve, C.; Rubio, R. G.;
9 Luengo, G. S., Adsorption of poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride)—sodium methyl-
10 cocoyl-taurate complexes onto solid surfaces. *Colloids Surf. A* **2016**, *505*, 150-157. doi:
11 10.1016/j.colsurfa.2016.03.003.
- 12 44. Mohanty, P. S.; Paloli, D.; Crassous, J. J.; Zaccarelli, E.; Schurtenberger, P., Effective
13 interactions between soft-repulsive colloids: Experiments, theory, and simulations. *J. Chem.*
14 *Phys.* **2014**, *140*, 094901. doi: 10.1063/1.4866644.
- 15 45. Nesder, P.; Passvogel, M.; Helm, C. A., Influence of Polymer Molecular Weight on
16 the Parabolic and Linear Growth Regime of PDADMAC/PSS Multilayers. *Macromolecules*
17 **2013**, *46*, 5622-5629. doi: 10.1021/ma400333f.
- 18 46. Ortmann, T.; Ahrens, H.; Lawrenz, F.; Groening, A.; Nestler, P.; Guenther, J.-U.;
19 Helm, C. A., Lipid Monolayers and Adsorbed Polyelectrolytes with Different Degrees of
20 Polymerization. *Langmuir* **2014**, *30*, 6768-6779. doi: 10.1021/la5001478.
- 21 47. Dautzenberg, H., *Polyelectrolytes : formation, characterization, and application*.
22 Hanser Publishers: New York, United States of America, 1994.
- 23 48. Dobrynin, A. V.; Rubinstein, M., Theory of polyelectrolytes in solutions and at
24 surfaces. *Prog. Polym. Sci.* **2005**, *30*, 1049-1118. doi:10.1016/j.progpolymsci.2005.07.006.
- 25 49. Faucher, J. A.; Goddard, E. D., Influence of surfactants on the sorption of a cationic
26 polymer by keratinous substrates. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **1976**, *55*, 313-319. doi:
27 10.1016/0021-9797(76)90039-4.
- 28 50. Goddard, E. D.; Ananthapadmanabhan, K. P., *Application of Polymer–Surfactant*
29 *Systems*. Marcel Dekker: New York-USA, 1998; Vol. 77.
- 30 51. Guzmán, E.; Ritacco, H.; Rubio, J. E. F.; Rubio, R. G.; Ortega, F., Salt-induced
31 changes in the growth of polyelectrolyte layers of poly(diallyldimethylammoniumchloride)
32 and poly(4-styrene sulfonate of sodium). *Soft Matter* **2009**, *5*, 2130-2142. doi:
33 10.1039/b901193e.
- 34 52. Chen, P.; Kwok, D. Y.; Prokop, R. M.; del Rio, O. I.; Sunsar, S. S.; Neumann, A. W.,
35 Axisymmetric Drop Shape Analysis (ADSA) and its applications. In *Drops and Bubbles in*
36 *Interfacial Research*, Möbius, D.; Miller, R., Eds. Elsevier Science B.V.: Amsterdam, The
37 Netherlands, 1998; Vol. 6, pp 61-139. doi: 10.1016/S1383-7303(98)80019-7.
- 38 53. Campbell, R. A.; Wacklin, H. P.; Sutton, I.; Cubitt, R.; Fragneto, G., FIGARO: the
39 new horizontal neutron reflectometer at the ILL. *Eur. Phys. J. Plus* **2011**, *126*, 107. doi:
40 10.1140/epjp/i2011-11107-8.
- 41 54. Nelson, A., Co-refinement of multiple-contrast neutron/X-ray reflectivity data using
42 MOTOFIT. *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* **2006**, *39*, 273. doi:10.1107/s0021889806005073.
- 43 55. Abeles, F., Sur la propagation des ondes electromagnetiques dans les milieux
44 stratifies. *Ann. Phys. (Paris, Fr.)* **1948**, *3*, 504-552.
- 45 56. Noskov, B. A.; Bilibin, A. Y.; Lezov, A. V.; Loglio, G.; Filippov, S. K.; Zorin, I. M.;
46 Miller, R., Dynamic surface elasticity of polyelectrolyte solutions. *Colloids Surf. A* **2007**,
47 *298*, 115-122. doi:10.1016/j.colsurfa.2006.12.003
- 48 57. Fainerman, V. B.; Lylyk, S. V.; Aksenenko, E. V.; Makievski, A. V.; Petkov, J. T.;
49 Yorke, J.; Miller, R., Adsorption layer characteristics of Triton surfactants: 1. Surface tension
PDADMAC+SLMT at air / water interface

- 1 and adsorption isotherms. *Colloids Surf. A* **2009**, *334*, 1-7. doi:
2 10.1016/j.colsurfa.2008.09.015.
- 3 58. Schulze-Zachau, F.; Braunschweig, B., Structure of Polystyrenesulfonate/Surfactant
4 Mixtures at Air–Water Interfaces and Their Role as Building Blocks for Macroscopic Foam.
5 *Langmuir* **2017**, *33*, 3499-3508. doi: 10.1021/acs.langmuir.7b00400.
- 6 59. Asnacios, A.; Langevin, D.; Argillier, J. F., Mixed monolayers of cationic surfactants
7 and anionic polymers at the air-water interface: Surface tension and ellipsometry studies. *Eur.*
8 *Phys. J. B* **1998**, *5*, 905-911. doi: 10.1007/s100510050516.
- 9 60. Noskov, B. A.; Grigoriev, D. O.; Lin, S. Y.; Loglio, G.; Miller, R., Dynamic Surface
10 Properties of Polyelectrolyte/Surfactant Adsorption Films at the Air/Water Interface:
11 Poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride) and Sodium Dodecylsulfate. *Langmuir* **2007**, *23*,
12 9641-9651. doi: 10.1021/la700631t.
- 13 61. Monteux, C.; Williams, C. E.; Meunier, J.; Anthony, O.; Bergeron, V., Adsorption of
14 Oppositely Charged Polyelectrolyte/Surfactant Complexes at the Air/Water Interface:
15 Formation of Interfacial Gels. *Langmuir* **2003**, *20*, 57-63. doi: 10.1021/la0347861.
- 16 62. Jaganathan, M.; Dhathathreyan, A., Conformational transitions of Cytochrome c in
17 sub-micron sized capsules at air/buffer interface. *Langmuir* **2014**, *30*, 11356–11365. doi:
18 10.1021/la5024696.
- 19 63. Fainerman, V. B.; Kovalchuk, V. I.; Aksenenko, E. V.; Miller, R., Dilational
20 Viscoelasticity of Adsorption Layers Measured by Drop and Bubble Profile Analysis: Reason
21 for Different Results. *Langmuir* **2016**, *32*, 5500–5509. doi: 10.1021/acs.langmuir.6b01134.
22